

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE
TEACHING

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Abstract. *In recent years, innovative technologies are becoming an integral part of human life in any spheres. Especially, in education, integration of innovative technologies in English language teaching has transforming traditional teaching approaches. This thesis explores numerous technological tools and innovative methods that can help to enhance language learning among learners, including online platforms, multimedia resources and mobile assisted language learning, also artificial intelligence. By clarifying benefits and challenges of implementing innovative technologies, the study aims to provide essential and useful outcomes for educators in not only language teaching but also learning language by gaining effective ways or strategies.*

Key words: *innovative technologies, online platforms, multimedia resources mobile assisted language learning, artificial intelligence, effective ways or strategies.*

Introduction

In this technological century, innovative technologies have become an important component of education. Considerably, English language teaching by innovative technologies can support more unprecedented opportunities for educators, in which engaging, collaborating and developing critical thinking.

The study demonstrates more facilitated language teaching practices by achieving advancements in implementing innovative technologies in English language teaching with creating more modern learning environment for learners. It explores the innovative tools and benefits learners can reach, along with challenges they can face in this implementation process.

Innovative technologies in English language teaching

Online platforms. Online platforms like Learning Management Systems such as Moodle, Google classroom, Canvas can support available learning environment both teachers and learners in case of facilitating communication atmosphere, enabling sharing of resources, assignments and feedback. By the way, they allow students to track their progress that signing learning achievements. They can contribute significantly to boost learners interest to language learning with their accessibility and enjoyable process.

Multimedia resources. In today's life, Multimedia resources including videos, podcasts and interactive games are playing an essential role in language teaching. Because they create different learning styles like visual, auditory and kinesthetic learning opportunities. For example, utilizing videos in language learning like YouTube platform can give various opportunities like distance learning, independent learning environment and following self-time management for watching for learners.

Mobile assisted language learning. MALL- mobile assisted language learning is also plays crucial role in language learning of students. That's why, most educators use different mobile application in order to facilitate their teaching process. In today's modernized mobile apps, we can find lots of beneficial tools in improving language skills.

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For instance, students can enhance their listening skills or speaking skill by communicating AI and just receiving feedback on pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary for their next practice.

Benefits of innovative technologies in language teaching

One of the advantageous sides of innovative technologies in ELT boost language learning by increasing motivation and engagement through interactive, multimedia content. They facilitate collaboration, remote access and making learning process more dynamic and accessible.

Enhancing engagement. Innovative technologies can significantly increase learner engagement. Interactive and platforms and multimedia resources make learning fun and capture student's attention.

Improved collaboration. Technology creates collaborative atmosphere among students.

Online discussion platforms and group projects enable students to work together, exchange ideas and give or receive feedback.

Challenges of incorporating innovative technologies

Overutilization of technology. Excessive dependence on technology can reduce essential face to face communication among students. Educators must keep a balance between traditional learning methods and technology integration.

Teacher readiness. Educators sometimes lack the skills or confidence to integrate new tools effectively, needing ongoing professional development. Because, ongoing professional development is essential to equip teachers with the knowledge and skills needed to utilize these tools effectively.

Conclusion

The integration of innovative technologies in English language teaching offers numerous benefits, including increased engagement, improved collaboration. However, the educators must also manage challenges like over reliance on digital tools and teacher readiness for integrating innovative technologies.

Innovative technologies have revolutionized the field of English Language Teaching by making learning more engaging, accessible and engageable. By embracing technology thoughtfully, educators can create dynamic and inclusive learning environment that prepare learners for a globalized future.

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